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Abstract:

This report considers the usability and usefulness aspects of services, tools, procedures, and data originating from WP9 (*Data Communities*). This report is linked to SSHOC D9.2 (*Midterm evaluation report*), which provides an overview of these products and of how they have been or will be made available to the data communities for which they are primarily intended.

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Executive Summary

This report presents information about how tools produced in the context of WP9 (*Data Communities*) have been received in their intended user communities. This emphasis on usability and usefulness is applied to, respectively to the following tools:

- The Ethnic Minorities and Migration (EMM) Survey Registry, that has been developed in Task 9.2 (Ethnic and Migration Studies)
- The pilot Knowledge Graph (KG) for Electoral Studies that has been developed in Task 9.3 (Data Community Project: Electoral Studies & EURHISFIRM)
- The pilot RESTORE platform for integrating data of different kinds in Heritage Science, that has been developed in Task 9.4 (Heritage Science and Humanities).

These three tools are in different stages of development and roll-out to their respective user communities. Furthest developed is the EMM Survey Registry. It exists in a well-developed beta version that has evolved with extensive input from potential users. It attracts hundreds of unique users per months which attests in and of itself to its usability, as well as to the clear need in the community of EMM researchers for a tool of this kind. While the tool will be improved further, it is evident that it can be considered as an unmitigated success already in its current version.

The other two tools --the pilot Knowledge Graph (KG) in Electoral Studies and the RESTORE data pilot for Heritage Science-- have each reached an alpha-version stage by November 2021, and both will be developed further in the months to come. The KG has been subjected to an internal functionality test by a small group of experts from the field, and subsequently has been evaluated more extensively by a more 'typical' group of end-users from its intended audience. This resulted in two clear outcomes: (1) there is strong enthusiasm about the potential of the KG and the current implementation, as reflected in a usability score just shy of 'good', and high perceived usefulness for researchers at different stages of their career; and (2) a number of weaknesses were flagged up that need to be addressed before the KG can claim to have reached beta-version status.

The RESTORE data pilot has been developed with strong input from experts from the various domains addressed by it and its main aspects have been validated successfully by these experts. The next stage will consist of a focus-group try-out with a more 'typical' group of end-users, to be conducted in the coming months. The continued intensive involvement of domain experts testifies to their positive perception of the usefulness of the RESTORE platform for their own work as well as for wider audiences of end-users.

At their current stages of development, it is already clear that each of these products represents a support for research in their respective domains that goes beyond what is currently available and that caters to actual needs of their respective data/user communities.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

AUSSDA	Austrian Social Science Data Archive
CESSDA ERIC	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
CIDOC - CRM	International Committee for Documentation - Conceptual Reference Model
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (Italy)
CSV	Comma Separated Values
DANS	Data Archiving and Networked Services
EAC	Exact Audio Copy
EMM	Ethnic and Migrant Minority
E/R model	Entity/Relation model
EQB	European Question Bank
FAIR	F indability, A ccessibility, I nteroperability, and R eusability
GESIS	Gesellschaft Sozialwissenschaftlicher Infrastruktureinrichtungen eV (German Social Science Infrastructure Services) – Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences
GLU	Gruppo di Lavoro per l'Usabilità
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
KG	Knowledge Graph
OVI-CNR	Istituto Opera del Vocabolario Italiano
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RESTORE	Smart A ccess t o Digital Heritage and M emory
SSHOC	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud
SUS	System Usability Scale
SWC	Semantic Web Company

TEI	Text Encoding Initiative
Turtle	Terse RDF Triple Language
UKDA	UK Data Archive
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
WoS	Web of Science
XML-EAD	Extensible Markup Language – Encoded Archival Description

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1. Introduction and purpose

This report constitutes Deliverable D9.3, known in the Description of Action as *Usability Evaluation Report*. Jointly with a previous report --D9.2 (*Midterm Evaluation Report*)¹-- it centres on the services, tools, procedures and data originating from WP9 (*Data Communities*).

As explained in this earlier report, the aims of D9.2 and D9.3 do overlap in non-negligible ways, which led to the decision to try and avoid unnecessary duplication by framing D9.2 as an explicit precursor of the current D9.3 report: “D9.2 focusses particularly on the description of the products emanating from WP9, while D9.3 will emphasise in as much detail as possible their usage in the various user communities and the feedback deriving from that usage” (D9.2, p.7).

As was the case for the D9.2 report, this report concentrates on three user communities that have been represented in Work Package 9 (Data Communities) from its inception: Ethnic and Migration Studies (Task T9.2), Electoral Studies (Task T9.3) and Heritage Science (Task 9.4). Other data communities that were included at later moments (*EURHISFIRM* and *RESILIENCE*) were not tasked within WP9 with producing services, tools, procedures or data, and are therefore not focussed upon in D9.2 or in this report.

The structure of this report reflects the qualitatively distinct character of what has been developed in the various tasks of WP9: each is reported upon in a separate section. Thus Section 2 reports on usability aspects of the work by Ethnic and Migration Studies, Section 3 does so for Electoral Studies, and Section 4 does so for Heritage Science. Section 5 concludes.

2. T9.2: Ethnic and Migration Studies

2.1 Introduction

T9.2 represents the ethnic and migration studies data community of SSHOC. To date, this data community has produced one publicly available and user-facing service, the EMM (Ethnic and Migrant

¹ See: Van der Eijk, Cees, Ami Saji, Carmen Di Meo & Emiliano Degl'Innocenti. (2021). D9.2 Midterm evaluation report (v1.0). *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5579235> (accessed 20-11-2021).

Minority) Survey Registry, important documentation of which can be found in Saji and Morales (2020a, 2020b) and Saji, Barjan and Douchet (2021).²

This service, which launched in spring 2020, currently displays detailed and structured information (i.e. metadata) for more than 1,500 quantitative surveys that have been undertaken with EMM populations in more than 30 different European countries. To maximise discovery and re-use of the EMM surveys it covers, the EMM Survey Registry also offers various user-friendly functionalities that allow its metadata to be easily leveraged and exploited by academic researchers, non-academic researchers and policy-oriented professionals. Moreover, vetted and approved users who are also data producers, are able to help expand the EMM Survey Registry's metadata collection by submitting new metadata via an online form (made available on the service's back-end interface).

Given the strides already made in developing the EMM Survey Registry, T9.2 is on track to deliver the final version of the service before the end of SSHOC. This final version will not only have a more expansive metadata collection (current estimate is over 1,700 EMM surveys from 34 different European countries) but will also likely include minor enhancements to further enrich the user experience.

2.2 Collecting and addressing feedback from users of the EMM Survey Registry

The EMM Survey Registry has been conceptualized and conceived as a service to benefit the various stakeholders of EMM surveys. As such, T9.2 has regularly been engaging different prospective users of the service throughout the design and development process.

For instance, a wide range of external user testers were identified and tasked with rigorously scrutinizing and assessing the pre-alpha and alpha versions of the EMM Survey Registry (see Table 1). This, in turn, has allowed the currently available beta version to: (a) be fully functional with all of the desired core functionalities, (b) benefit from a user-centric and user-driven design, and (c) be a single access point to useful and relevant information about existing EMM surveys.

² See: Ami Saji, & Laura Morales. (2020a). D9.4 Database with the metadata of surveys to EMMs across Europe (v1.0). *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4558307> (accessed 20-11-2021); Saji, Ami, & Morales, Laura. (2020b). Reusing and sharing metadata: A case study of quantitative survey research on the integration of ethnic and migrant minorities (EMMs) across Europe. 12th Annual European DDI User Conference (EDDI20). *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4305692> (accessed Aug 2021); Saji, Ami, Barjan, Isabella & Douchet, Léa. (2021). EMM SURVEY REGISTRY Back-end user guide <https://ethmigsurveydatahub.eu/emmregistry/user-guide-beta-version-emm-survey-registry/> (accessed 20/11/2021).

Table 1: Example of key suggestions collected from user testers of the pre-alpha and alpha versions of the EMM Survey Registry

Key suggestion provided	Suggested by?	When implemented
As part of the basic filtering, include options that allow a user to easily find surveys conducted with specific EMM populations, as well as those where the datasets, documentation, and/or questionnaires are available for re-use	Academic researchers; policy analysts at think tanks, EU agencies, and international organizations	Included in the alpha version
Set up the advanced filtering to be an extended version of the basic filtering by adding options about the main topics of the surveys and related to methodology	Academic researchers; policy analysts at think tanks, EU agencies	Included in the alpha version
As part of the overall metadata provided for a survey, include information about whether the survey has been completed or not	Academic researchers	Included in the alpha version
As part of the overall metadata provided for a survey, include information about whether the survey was conducted with the general population (where EMMs were included as respondents) or strictly with EMMs	Academic researchers; policy analysts at think tanks, EU agencies, and international organizations	Included in the alpha version
As part of the overall metadata provided for a subnational survey, include detailed information about the subnational coverage (e.g., whether the survey was conducted in urban vs. suburban vs. rural locations)	Policy analysts at EU agencies	Included in the alpha version
For the short description provided for each survey (when viewing the full list of surveys covered by the EMM Survey Registry), include information about whether the survey was conducted with the general population (where EMMs were included as respondents) or strictly with EMMs	Academic researchers; policy analyst at an international organization	Included in the beta version
Distinguish more clearly how to access and implement the simple and advanced filtering options	Policy analyst at an international organization	Included in the beta version
Revise the formatting and font styles of the metadata to improve readability, particularly for those with vision impairments	Academic researchers	Included in the beta version

Table 1 (continued)

More clearly identify the metadata explaining how to access the survey datasets, documentation, questionnaires, etc.	Data archiving and curation expert	Included in the beta version
Add features (e.g. navigation menu) that allows a user to more easily navigate the metadata across the different surveys, as well as the metadata of a given survey	Academic researchers; data archiving and curation experts; policy analysts at think tanks, EU agencies, and international organizations	Included in the beta version
For metadata where dates are mentioned, use the ISO date format	Data archiving and curation experts	Included in the beta version
For the online form, provide a short tip/explanation about what type of metadata to provide	Academic researchers; policy analysts at EU agencies	Included in the beta version
As part of the overall metadata provided for a survey, include information about whether the survey was conducted with the general population (where EMMs were included as respondents) or strictly with EMMs	Academic researchers; policy analysts at think tanks, EU agencies, and international organizations	Included in the alpha version

As for collecting feedback for the beta version, T9.2 has actively been liaising with its existing user base and connecting with new prospective users to understand the current user experience of the EMM Survey Registry. Thus far, T9.2 has learned, most notably through a short survey, that users have been able to use the service as a starting point for discovering and learning about existing survey studies (including their potential for re-use) related to their specific interests, due to the rich and reliable metadata provided for each of the surveys. T9.2 has also learned that users, while already finding the service to be user-friendly and comprehensive, would mainly like two different types of improvements to be considered for the final version: (1) enhancing the usability of the online form (e.g. making it easier to scroll through the form, allowing a user to export information inputted into a form as a CSV file) and (2) expanding the type of metadata collected and offered for the surveys (e.g. including information about whether a survey was conducted at the EU-level). As such, T9.2 has created a “wish list” to document any improvement related feedback it receives; T9.2 will then assess, based on the available budget and resources, which of the requested improvements can realistically and feasibly be implemented by the conclusion of SSHOC.

2.3 Understanding the users of the EMM Survey Registry

Since October 2020, the landing page of the EMM Survey Registry has been collecting usage data using Google Analytics (see Graph 1). Each month, around 300-400 unique users visit the EMM Survey Registry, with usage increasing in months where events promoting the service have occurred or taken place. Moreover, the service has successfully welcomed users from across the globe, most notably from Europe (89%) and the Americas (7%).

While Google Analytics does not collect information about the professional backgrounds of the users, such information has been collected, as part of the registration process for the two SSHOC webinars about the EMM Survey Registry. For example, for these two webinars, around 80-90% of the registrants identified as working for a research-focused institution or as a researcher. Additionally, for the second webinar, the registrants were primarily from the scientific disciplines of political science (60%), sociology (10%), and geography (10%).

Finally, as part of its on-going outreach and dissemination activities related to the EMM Survey Registry, T9.2 has learned informally about the diversity of the service’s user base. Specifically, T9.2 has interacted with users who are (non)academic researchers from various social science disciplines, as well as policy-oriented professionals working for local and national governments, think tanks, EU agencies, and international organizations.

Graph 1: Number of unique users per month (10/2020 – 10/2021)

3. T9.3: Electoral Studies

3.1 Introduction

The alpha version of the Knowledge Graph in Electoral Studies can be evaluated in many different ways. In this report the focus is first of all on its usability for its intended audience. This audience has been specified in D9.7 (*Design and Planning of Knowledge Graph in Electoral Studies*)³ as follows

“The pilot-KG is directed towards different scholars in the field of electoral studies. It is envisaged that the KG will, in due course, also be of relevance to other end-users, such as journalists, think tanks, government agencies (including electoral commissions and election regulators), corporations, political parties and politicians, and individual citizens. Yet, during the development phase and the evaluation of the resulting KG the focus will be primarily on academic scholars.” (Van der Eijk et al. 2020: 19).

A dedicated online workshop/focus group was organised as a test and feedback opportunity involving members of the intended audience as described above. This workshop was conducted in November 2021 and included 18 participants who were purposefully recruited. The group comprised participants from a variety of national backgrounds (Britain, Germany, Austria, the Netherlands, Belgium, the Netherlands, Italy) all active in academic work in a variety of countries (Britain, Ireland, Germany, the Netherlands, Belgium, USA). Qua academic seniority they encompassed a wide spectrum: lecturers and professors with considerable experience, lecturers and professors with less experience, postdocs, PhD students, and MA students. They all had an active interest in electoral studies. After having been familiarised in the workshop to the current version of the Knowledge Graph by way of a general introduction and a demonstration, participants were invited to perform themselves a few typical tasks with the KG (during the workshop as well as at some time of their own choosing, afterwards). The participants were asked to share their experiences, comments, suggestions, and evaluations in an unstructured form as well as by way of a short, structured questionnaire. This report summarises the feedback obtained from this event.

3.2 Usability

An overarching perspective on the experiences of the participants with the KG can be obtained from a so-called systems usability scale (SUS) that was included in the structured questionnaire. The SUS was

³ See: van der Eijk Cees, Kritzinger Sylvia, Partheymüller Julia, Kaltenböck Martin, Ahmeti Albin, & Karampatakis Sotirios. (2020). SSHOC D9.7 Design and Planning of Knowledge Graph in Electoral Studies (v1.0). *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3824266> (accessed 20/11/2021).

originally proposed by Brooke (1996) and has since been used widely and successfully to obtain end-user experiences and evaluations with products operated via a user interface, such as websites, mobile phones, voice response systems and so forth. Because it is ‘technology agnostic’ the SUS is also suitable to evaluate the KG in electoral studies. Moreover, because the SUS has been used in thousands of studies worldwide, any scores obtained can easily be compared with established standards and validated substantive meanings of scores. The SUS was implemented in the questionnaire by way of the following 10 items:

- I think that I would like to use this KG frequently
- I found the KG unnecessarily complex
- I thought the KG was easy to use
- I think I would need support of a technical person to be able to use this KG
- I found the various functions in this KG were well integrated
- I thought there was too much inconsistency in this KG
- I would imagine that most people would learn to use this KG very quickly
- I found the KG very cumbersome to use
- I felt very confident using the KG
- I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this KG

Five response options were provided for each of these items, ranging from (1) strongly disagree to (5) strongly agree. The responses to the ten items can be combined into an overall score that ranges from 0 to 100 (see Brooke 1996). The average SUS score for the KG was 70.0. To put this score in perspective, Bangor, Kortum and Miller (2008, 2009) are referred to, who reviewed thousands of studies in which the SUS was included and who conclude that “products that scored in the 90s were exceptional, products that scored in the 80s were good, and products that scored in the 70s were acceptable. Anything below a 70 had usability issues that were cause for concern” (2009:115). They also compared the SUS score to respondents’ evaluations as expressed on a seven-point adjective anchored Likert scale⁴, which showed a very strong correlation with SUS scores ($r=.82$). The descriptive adjectives allow a SUS score to be interpreted in common language (Bangor, Kortum and Miller 2009:118). The SUS of 70, which was obtained for the KG, falls between the calibrated meaning of ‘OK’ (which has a mean SUS score of 50.9) and ‘Good’ (which has a mean SUS score of 71.4). As such, the evaluation of the KG falls just short of ‘good’, but also reflects the presence of some non-negligible usability issues.

The quantitative information about the usability of the KG corresponds with some of the qualitative feedback from the participants, which also shows a mixture of excitement about the KG and clear awareness of aspects that need improvement, as expressed in comments such as:

“I believe that this is a great tool which I would love to use in the future”

⁴ The seven categories of this scale were worded as follows: Worst Imaginable / Awful / Poor / OK / Good / Excellent / Best Imaginable.

“I do really appreciate the ideas behind the KG”

“I really like the tool. I think some of the machine learning needs a little more tweaking though”

and

“I like the idea of this overall. Seems like it could be a very helpful tool for me personally”.

3.3 Usefulness for specific audiences

Apart from questions about the participants’ own views on the usability of the KG, the structured questionnaire contained also a few questions about the kind of users for who the KG would be particularly useful. Table 2 shows the four kinds of users that were specified, as well as the average of the pre-coded responses which ranged from 1 (‘not useful at all’) to 5 (‘extremely useful’):

The perceived usefulness of the KG is seen as particularly high for academic users, almost irrespective of their seniority or academic status. To some extent this may reflect that the group of participants consisted entirely of students of academically employed, who perhaps have some difficulty in envisaging the reasons for non-academics to use the KG. Later workshops with non-academics as participants should clarify how they perceive the relevance of the KG for their own work.

Table 2: Perceived usefulness of the Knowledge Graph in Electoral Studies for various kinds of end-users.

Mean score of responses ranging from 1 (not useful at all) to 5 (extremely useful):

Undergraduate and Masters’ students	4.2
PhD students and Postdocs	4.4
Seasoned academics	4.1
Non-academics (journalists, officials in election administration, etc.)	3.8

3.4 Weaknesses in the alpha version of the KG

Much of the qualitative feedback, and some sets of questions in the structured questionnaire provide specific information about aspects of the KG that could be improved, often with very helpful suggestions of how an improved version would look like. Grouping these comments and suggestions in a few broad categories, it is visible that they relate in particular to:

- (Lack of) user control over the interface. For example, users can specify in their queries the year in which a publication or dataset appeared, but not a time span such as ‘after 2015’ or ‘between 2010 and 2019’. Also, authors are sorted by the number of their publications without the option to have them sorted alphabetically.
- Suggestions for improving the categories in various of the ‘facets’ that are used in specifying queries (e.g., include sub-categories for different kinds of publications, as well as for ‘concepts and theories’.
- Incomplete coverage of all facets for ingested publications or datasets, which becomes visible when exporting results.
- Suggestions for improved layout of results (e.g., ‘similar’ results as the ones returned for one’s query are indicated by an icon, while a text string would be more informative).
- Suggestions to include a way for end-users to flag up and feed back errors of classification of the publications or data covered.
- Comments about the (poor) operating speed of the KG. Incidentally, this is not related to the design or architecture of the KG, but to its technical environment (capacity and bandwidth available on the servers hosting the KG and its database, which is not optimised for multiple users in the development phase).

Many of these suggestions can be implemented in next versions of the KG, some may be requiring more effort than that, but, without a doubt, all specific suggestions have been helpful and reflected a gratifying level of intellectual involvement by the participants of the workshop.

3.5 Competing tools for searching information

One might ask the question how researchers currently tend to satisfy their needs for searching relevant information about publications and data. Knowledge about this helps –indirectly— to shed some light on the user-potential of KGs. For this reason, the structured questionnaire included a small battery of items about the frequency with which respondents’ make use of the following possibilities to query for publications or data in the field of Electoral Studies: Google Scholar; Web of Science (WoS); Web browsers (Firefox, Google, Chrome, etc.); the CESSDA Catalogue⁵; Catalogues of data archives such as GESIS, DANS, UKDA, AUSSDA, etc, and one’s University Library. Responses could be given on a 5-point adjective anchored scale comprising the following options: (1) never; (2) rarely; (3) occasionally; (4) regularly; (5) frequently. Table 3 summarises the responses in terms of the mean of the responses.

The responses to this question reflect two different phenomena: on the one hand awareness of and familiarity with the tool in question, and on the other hand its perceived usefulness for identifying the

⁵ The CESSDA catalogue contains the metadata of all data in the holdings of CESSDA’s service providers. It aims to be a one-stop-shop for search and discovery, enabling effective access to European social science research data (see: <https://www.cessda.eu>).

required information. Not knowing about the existence of a tool will necessarily result in a response that one ‘never’ uses it, although this response may, obviously, also derive from a perception that the tool in question is not very helpful. Three of the tools presented did not generate a single response that they were used ‘never’, implying that respondents are in any case aware of their availability. These three are Google Scholar, Web browsers, and the University Library. The other three – Web of Science, the CESSDA Catalogue and Catalogues of national data archives such as GESIS, DANS, UKDA and AUSSDA– all showed some respondents responding that they ‘never’ used them. In view of the specific content of these tools and their functionality that is dedicated to research purposes, it is unlikely that these ‘never’ responses reflect perceptions of low usefulness, while the more likely interpretation is that these tools are unknown to some of the respondents. Interpreting the responses in this way suggests that ‘1’ scores do not reflect perceived usefulness of these tools; omitting these responses from the calculated mean (as presented in the most rightward column of Table 3) then yields a reflection of perceived usefulness. Irrespective of how one wants to interpret the ‘1’ scores, it is obvious that the Google Scholar is currently a tool that is used almost universally and frequently to search for relevant information about research. The implication of this is that, in due course, a KG must add functionality and usability surpassing Scholar Google to be likely to be taken up as a part of end-users’ repertoire of tools. Given the fact that all the respondents use Google Scholar regularly or frequently, their feedback and responses with respect to usability and usefulness of the KG are encouraging, as they clearly perceive the potential of this new tool positively. Yet, at the same time it is obvious that the full scale of the desired functionality of the KG has not yet been obtained.

Table 3: Reported frequency of use of tools for searching information about publications or data in the field of Electoral Studies.

Mean scores on 1-5 response scale (1=never; 5=frequently) and on responses excluding ‘1’ scores:

	Mean score	Mean score excluding ‘1’
Google Scholar	4.9	4.9
Web of Science	2.3	3.0
Web browsers	3.8	3.8
CESSDA data catalogue	1.7	2.2
Catalogues of data archives	2.8	3.0
University Library	2.9	2.9

Although somewhat tangential to the main purpose of this report, Table 3 also illustrates clearly that the mere presence of extremely functional and well-crafted dedicated tools is not sufficient for ensuring them being taken up by research communities. Even among this relatively well-informed group of participants, there is clear lack of familiarity with, as well as limited perceived usefulness of such infrastructural tools and resources as Web of Science, the CESSDA catalogue, and the catalogues of national data archives. Thus, for the KG as well as for other products that will emanate from SSHOC, effective and widespread dissemination and training remains of the utmost importance.

4. T9.4: Heritage Science

4.1 Development of the RESTORE pilot and validation by domain experts

As referred in D9.2 (*Midterm Evaluation Report*)⁶, the RESTORE data pilot involves the development of a digital platform for the recovery, integration, accessibility and reuse of digital resources, either provided by GLAM (Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museums) institutions and/or Heritage science research institutes (Degl'Innocenti et al. 2021).⁷ More specifically, this pilot aims to achieve the integration of data initially coming from three different partners in the field of Cultural Heritage and Heritage Science. These partners are, respectively, the Archivio di Stato of Prato (which epitomises the contributions of archives in this field), the Museo di Palazzo Pretorio, Prato (which exemplifies how museums participate in Cultural Heritage and Heritage Science), and the Istituto Opera del Vocabolario Italiano (OVI-CNR) which characterises the role of libraries in this field. Further extensions of the same approach will be able to integrate other data sources. The information and data that derive from each of these kinds of institutions is based on different cataloguing standards each with their own metadata schemas and encoding formats. These differently structured data are to be integrated in the RESTORE pilot in a so-called "PERSON - EVENT - OBJECT" form. This reflects the chosen semantic modelling approach (based on triples) for data integration, which is more appropriate for highly unstructured information than traditional relational databases that use the E/R (Entity/Relation) model. The resulting data are serialized as RDF (Resource Description Framework) triples, a typical formal logic construct that allows data encoding with an explicit emphasis on their denotative properties instead of their connotative aspects. This, in turn, makes it possible to run computational services (i.e., inferences) using reasoners and other similar technologies. This chosen approach combines essential and common background information and allows multiple integrated data views, which are useful to both domain experts, citizen scientists and generic users.

In this specific case, the goal was to integrate separate datasets that have been produced in isolation over the past decades, each based on its own scientific focus, each using different technologies, and each reflecting its own semantic perspective. For the sake of effectiveness, in most of the cases similarities between the original datasets were mainly restricted to a core set of entities: person(s), place(s) and event(s).

⁶ See Van der Eijk, Cees, Ami Saji, Carmen Di Meo, & Emiliano Degl'Innocenti. (2021). D9.2 Midterm evaluation report (v1.0). *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5579235> (accessed 20-11-2021).

⁷ See: Degl'Innocenti, Emiliano, Carmen Di Meo, Francesco Coradeschi, Maurizio Sanesi, Elisa Brunoni, Athina Kritsotaki, & Eleni Tsoulouha. (2021). MS49 Heritage Science and Humanities Pilot alpha release (v1.0). *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5217113> (accessed 20 November 2021).

As stated, a semantic modelling approach was considered as the best option to represent these different kinds of data. The two most important reasons for this choice were, first, that it is less monolithic than the Entity/Relation model and more extendable in case of subsequent iterations of data integration. Second, the semantic modelling approach allows the preservation of the semantics and the data itself in the same structure (i.e.: the RDF triples).

The platform's general design choices have always been made in consultation between all the partners in this project, who have all subscribed to decisions about the technical and scientific data processing and conversion. Yet, over the course of the project some changes had to be made with respect to the selection criteria used in mapping information, which were deemed necessary to express the relevant aspect of all individual sources.

Recently, during a meeting with one of the main project partners, the State Archives of Prato, the developing team at the OVI-CNR was able to collect extensive feedback from domain experts on several, fundamental aspects of the mapping made on archival datasets which were converted to RDF format according to the CIDOC-CRM ontology. When working with archival data it is essential to be able to clearly identify subjects involved in the production of texts, letters, manuscripts and so on. This requires the appropriate identification of each piece of information involved in the composition of names, in their complete forms and their aliases and variant forms, as well as the toponyms and anthroponyms. Furthermore, normalization of titles and attributes, simple or composed forms of names, families and corporations played an important role in the data cleaning process. This is particularly pertinent in the case of the data provided by the State Archives of Prato, most of which originate from the Medieval age. In this case, it was essential to receive support from domain experts to distinguish the composition of names, in order to avoid confusion between what can be labelled as "person (name)", and what stands for, for instance, a toponymic indication "person (part of the name that expresses his/her/their provenance)". The involvement of domain experts in the mapping of archival data ensured that the final data representation is in accordance with relevant disciplinary expertise, and that their representation in the form of "entities", "properties", and "objects" can be considered valid.

From the collaboration with the pilot's partners, it has been experienced that the chosen user-friendly semantic data (and graph) navigation tool helped domain experts (archivists, museum curators etc.) to evaluate the efficiency and adequacy of the adopted data integration strategy. Such tools show the necessary information needed for communication with both academic and general end users. The same domain experts could therefore, in the course of subsequent testing stages, validate the choice of using CIDOC-CRM as the conceptual reference model and ontology, which fosters open access and FAIRification of the partners' data, without necessitating specific and overly narrow domain-related logics. To accomplish this modelling process, it was necessary to perform (and repeat) the following migrations:

- from native data formats, such as XML-EAD and EAC, ICCD, and TEI (to name a few) to a custom exchange format, with data represented in a tabular form;
- from this custom tabular format (CSV) to the required RDF/Turtle serialization.

To completely represent the whole complexity of the “cultural heritage object”, it was necessary to distinguish between two information levels. One referring to the material aspect and features of the object mapped, together with the information about its physical support, which is relevant for users interested in the tangible characteristics of Cultural Heritage (i.e.: Heritage Scientists); the other referring to the immaterial characteristics of the object itself, crucial for users interested in the intangible dimension of cultural heritage (i.e.: Social Sciences and Humanities researchers). This distinction is expressed by the CIDOC-CRM model, as the distinction between: E22 Man-Made Object as the physical document/object, and the E73 Information Object, as its information content.

Other design choices with respect to mapping strategies that were successfully validated by domain experts included

- The identification of the single “resource (object)”, which stands as the centre of the mapping model, by one URI (ID), as its unique and unambiguous persistent identifier;
- The linking to the single URI of the following information, for both documents (archival documents and collections, letters, literary texts etc) and other cultural heritage artifacts:
 - Title;
 - Signature (i.e., shelfmark);
 - Iconography (subjects);
 - Repositories;
 - Actual location;
 - Former and current keeper(s);
 - Person responsible for the production event;
 - Production event (Creation);
 - Place of production event;
 - Date or period of production event;
 - Author of creation;
 - Date of birth/death of authors;
 - Corporate bodies or families or institutions involved in the production event;
 - Exchange of letters (sending and receiving);
 - Transfers of custody;
 - Materials of the mapped object;
 - Physical description of the mapped object;
 - Physical description of the support;
 - Genre (of object);
 - Type of entities;
 - ICONCLASS description;
 - Number of object components;
 - Object measures;
 - State of conservation of the object;
 - Notes.

4.2 User validation

To ensure the effectiveness of the data integration strategy and to evaluate its usability for the relevant communities, the beta version of the RESTORE platform, once released, will be tested with a User Research Protocol, inspired from the qualitative research methods of a generative type (focus group). The main purpose will be to collect user-generated experiences, observations, comments, suggestions and other feedback.

The focus group will be centered around “USER STORIES”, i.e. a list of possible actions that are imagined to represent the needs of users willing to research and to interact with the digital environment of the RESTORE pilot. The imagined tasks will be significant and realistic, meaning that they will correspond to activities that users usually do when visiting the partner’s websites. The testing protocol and material were developed on the basis of the Guidelines contained in the document named “Protocollo eGLU 2.1”, made by the Usability Working Group GLU (Gruppo di Lavoro per l’Usabilità) and validated and signed by the “Dipartimento della Funzione Pubblica” (Italian Government Presidency of the Council of Ministers): *Linee guida di design per i servizi web della Pubblica Amministrazione | 5.1. Usabilità.*⁸

The focus group is structured as follows:

- Informative introduction in which the scope of the research is presented to the participating users;
- Active participation by the members of the focus group (tasks execution) / Observed by team members
- Administration of a structured user questionnaire (including System Usability Scale)
- Analysis and reporting of feedback, observations and questionnaire data.

The results from this focus group will be used for the final evaluation of the RESTORE pilot, which will be performed together with the partner institutions involved. This will lead in any case to:

- Documentation and guides of the development of the front-end of the RESTORE platform;
- A validation and usability for end-users report;
- An analysis of user behaviour in order to specify and implement the final version of a RESTORE knowledge graph.

As the RESTORE pilot constitutes the T9.4 case study, the testing protocol is a part of the final workflow defined by the project.

⁸ This document is accessible at:

http://www.funzionepubblica.gov.it/sites/funzionepubblica.gov.it/files/Protocollo_eGLU_2_1_19082015_DEF_2.pdf
(accessed 20 November 2021)

5. Conclusion

The previous sections have documented usability assessments of what has been wrought in the main tasks of WP9 for their respective data/user communities. Unavoidably, these assessments are not complete at the time of writing. After all, the SSHOC project has still a number of months to go before its conclusion, during which time the products of the different WP9-Tasks will be developed further and subjected to further user evaluations. Moreover, the work of the three Tasks has not reached the same stage at the time of writing.

Furthest developed of the tools and products reviewed in this report is the EMM Survey Registry. It exists in a well-developed beta version that has been developed with extensive input from potential users. It attracts hundreds of unique users per months (see Graph 1 and Section 2.3). This, in and of itself, attests to its usability, as well as to the clear need in the community of EMM researchers for a tool of this kind. Plans exist for further improvements and extensions of the Registry, as indicated in Section 2 of this report, which will only increase its usefulness for academic and non-academic researchers and for policymakers. But it is evident that in its current version can be considered as an unmitigated success.

The other two tools --the pilot Knowledge Graph (KG) in Electoral Studies and the RESTORE data pilot for Heritage Science-- have each reached an alpha-version stage by November 2021, and both are planned to be developed further in the months to come. The KG has been subjected to an internal functionality test by a small group of experts from the field, as reported in D9.10 (*User Community Feedback Report*)⁹. Later, in November 2021 the KG has been tested and evaluated by a more 'typical' group of end-users from its intended audience. This resulted in two clear outcomes: (1) there is strong enthusiasm about the potential of the KG and the current implementation, as reflected in a SUS-score of 70 (which is just shy of 'good') and high perceived usefulness of the KG for researchers at different stages of their career; and (2) a number of weaknesses were flagged up by end-users that need to be addressed before the KG can claim to have reached beta-version status.

The RESTORE data pilot has been developed with strong input from experts from the various domains addressed by it (Libraries, Archives, Museums and Heritage science research institutes). Various aspects of the RESTORE platform have been validated successfully by these experts, and the next stage will consist of a focus-group try-out with a more 'typical' group of end-users, to be conducted in the coming months. The continued intensive involvement of these domain experts testifies to their positive perception of the usefulness of the RESTORE platform for their own work as well as for wider audiences of end-users.

Although the three products whose usability was reviewed in this report have not yet reached equivalent stages of development and end-user testing and assessment, it is already clear that each represents a

⁹ See: Cees van der Eijk, & Julia Partheymüller. (2021). D9.10 User community feedback and usage report (v1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5579217> (accessed 20/11/2021).

development of research-support tools that go beyond what is currently available and that cater to actual needs of their respective data/user communities.

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